

CuSO₄·5H₂O catalyzed efficient one pot synthesis of α-amino nitriles

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Abstract : α-Amino nitriles are synthesized in a one pot three component coupling of aldehydes, amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide using catalytic amount of CuSO₄·5H₂O at ambient temperature.

Keywords : α-Amino nitriles, CuSO₄·5H₂O, aldehydes, amines, trimethylsilyl cyanide.

Introduction

α-Amino nitriles are versatile materials for the synthesis of a variety of vital molecules like amino acids¹, thiadiazoles², imidazoles³ and bioactive molecules like Saframycin A⁴ etc. Due to their large number of synthetic utilities, their efficient preparation is of great significance and continues to draw attention of organic chemists. The traditional method of their production is Strecker reaction⁵ which involved the use of established poison KCN. So clearly, some improvements were necessary. Therefore, some alternative cyanide transferring agents have been explored like diethyl phosphorocyanidate⁶, α-trimethylsilyloxy nitriles⁷, acetone cyanohydrin⁸, Et₂AlCN⁹ and trimethylsilyl cyanide¹⁰ etc. Out of these, non-alkali metal cyanide variants trimethylsilyl cyanide continue to be more attractive, safer and effective cyanide source for nucleophilic addition to imines. To facilitate its addition, suitable catalyst is necessary. To achieve this objective various Bronsted and Lewis acids are reported recently. These include acids like H₂SO₄ and its derivatives SiO₂ : H₂SO₄^{11a}, NH₂SO₃H^{11b} and Lewis acids like Zn halides^{11c}, InCl₃^{11d}, La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O or GdCl₃·6H₂O^{11e}. For a most recent report rhodium(III) iodide hydrate is also used for the synthesis of α-amino nitriles¹².

These known procedures have several limitations like the use of strong acids, costly catalyst, require pre-preparation of catalyst and some of the catalysts are hygroscopic and even strong acids are difficult to handle. Over and above these limitations, several of these form corrosive and hazardous by-products during aqueous work-up. Recently, CuSO₄·5H₂O has been reported to be mild, cheap, readily available catalyst in several functional group transformations¹³. In continuation to our own investigation¹⁴ on CuSO₄·5H₂O as mild Lewis acid, here we report its use in the synthesis of amino nitriles in a one pot three component coupling of aldehydes, amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide at room temperature (Scheme 1).

In a typical case, a solution of benzaldehyde (0.21 g, 2 mmol), aniline (0.19 g, 2 mmol) and trimethylsilyl cyanide (0.20 g, 2 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) were stirred at room temperature. To this solution CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.05 g, 0.2 mmol) was added and the resulting solution was stirred for 50 min. After completion of reaction (vide TLC), excess of acetonitrile was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 mL). The organic layer was washed with saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (2 × 20 mL), brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of solvent gave

Scheme 1

crude product which was purified by recrystallization with benzene-petroleum ether mixture to afford 2-(*N*-anilino)-2-phenylacetonitrile **3a**, m.p. 72–73 °C (lit. 72–73 °C) in 94% yield. The product showed absorption at 2240 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ function. A broad singlet (D_2O exchangeable) was observed for NH in ^1H NMR spectrum of **3a** beside the other peaks. Similarly other aldehydes were coupled with a variety of amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide in presence of catalytic amount of $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to furnish α -amino nitriles **3b–p** in 81–96% yields (Table 1). The products thus obtained were characterized with IR, NMR and mass spectra.

A variety of aromatic, conjugated and heterocyclic aldehydes have been reacted with amines and TMSCN at room temperature to obtain α -amino nitriles (Table 1). Secondary amines such as morpholine, piperidine, pyrrolidine have also been employed along with aromatic amines. The reaction completes within 50–75 min and 10 mol% of catalyst is enough to facilitate the reaction to completion. The use of large amount of catalyst did not improve the yields or reduce the reaction time. Also, when reaction was carried out without catalyst it did not furnish desirable result and without the use of catalyst, reaction does proceeds significantly. It is worth mention-

Table 1. $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mediated synthesis of α -amino nitriles

Entry	Aldehydes	Amines	Products ^a	Time (min)	Yields (%) ^b	M.p. (°C) ^c
1		3a	50	94	72–73 (72–73)	
2		3b	55	92	95–96 (95–96)	
3		3c	55	90	Colorless oil	
4		3d	50	96	109–111 (109–112)	
5		3e	60	89	Colorless oil	
6		3f	65	87	120–122 (121–122)	
7		3g	60	92	74–76 (74–76)	
8		3h	65	96	Colorless oil	
9		3i	65	84	128–129 (128–129)	
10		3j	60	85	108–110	

Table-1 (contd.)

11		3k	55	84	117-118
12		3l	70	84	Colorless oil
13		3m	75	83	Colorless oil
14		3n	65	85	68-70 (68-70)
15		3o	65	84	101-102
16		3p	75	81	84-85

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples.

^bIsolated yields after recrystallization. ^cLit. m.p. in parenthesis.

ing here we did not observe the formation of any ring ruptured dyes as is observed in the past, rather nitriles are obtained in good yields. Certainly, during Schiff's base formation CuSO₄·5H₂O did not rupture the furan ring¹⁵ as the furan ring is very much sensitive to acids as well as bases.

Difficulties are always encountered when conjugated α-amino nitriles are to be produced. The conventional procedure produces alkaline medium and hence these methods are plagued with the formation of solvolysed or rearranged products¹⁶. This may be the result of solvents (alcohol or water) employed earlier in these methods. In contrast, in this procedure neither double bond migration is observed nor the formation of any solvolysed product rather normal nitriles are obtained in excellent yields.

In conclusion, the present protocol employing catalytic amount of CuSO₄·5H₂O, is an efficient and superior to already reported procedures, as it is mild, cost effective and one pot strategy for the preparation of α-amino nitriles. Further advantages of this protocol are less time consuming, high yields and work is simple and non hazardous. Also the present procedure is fairly general and is applicable to a variety of aromatic, conjugated and heterocyclic aldehydes which are coupled *in situ* with primary, secondary and aromatic amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide at room temperature.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent-grade chemicals were purchased from commercial source and used without further purification. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel-G (Merck).

General procedure for preparation of α-amino nitriles :

To a stirred solution of aldehyde (2 mmol), amine (2 mmol) and trimethylsilyl cyanide (2 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) at room temperature, CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.2 mmol) was added. The resulting solution was stirred for time indicated in Table 1. After completion of reaction (vide TLC), excess of acetonitrile was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 mL). The organic layer was washed with saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (2 × 20 mL), brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of solvent gave crude product which was purified by recrystallization with benzene-petroleum ether mixture to afford α-amino nitriles.

Selected spectral data :

2-(*N*-Anilino)-2-phenylacetonitrile (Table 1, Entry 1,

3a) : m.p. 72–73 °C; IR (KBr) : 3340, 2240 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.51 (2H, m), 7.30 (3H, t), 7.25 (2H, t, *J* 7.9 Hz), 6.92 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.72 (2H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 5.39 (1H, s), 4.03 (1H, br s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 146.7, 136.5, 130.4, 129.9, 128.8, 128.2, 127.2, 122.7, 117.2, 51.2.

2-Phenyl-2-(*N*-pyrrolidino)acetonitrile (Table 1, Entry 13, **3m**) : Colorless oil; IR (KBr) : 2229 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.54–7.42 (2H, m), 7.40–7.29 (3H, m), 4.48 (1H, s), 2.72–2.60 (4H, m), 1.90–1.69 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 135.6, 129.6, 129.1, 128.3, 117.8, 110.4, 60.3, 52.3.

2-(*N*-Morpholino)-2-phenylacetonitrile (Table 1, Entry 14, **3n**) : m.p. 68–70 °C; IR (KBr) : 2232 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.48–7.29 (5H, m), 4.78 (4H, t, *J* 4.5 Hz), 2.57 (4H, t, *J* 4.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 133.2, 130.7, 129.5, 129.2, 128.5, 116.5, 72.2, 62.3, 53.4.

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